

ScanRacer – Fast Track Annotation of Segmentation Masks in Volumetric Medical Images

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Introduction

With the rise of deep learning [1], we see a dramatic need of curated and annotated medical image data. In particular, in volumetric images, such annotations are extremely costly, as each slice has to be outlined individually to generate ground truth for the training of deep learning algorithms. Recently, a new initiative was founded that aims at encouraging patients to donate their medical image data [2]. In particular, this initiative also asks for permission to crowd-source the data annotation. This forms a basis to generate sufficient data for large-scale training of deep learning algorithms in medical image analysis.

Fig. 1. Illustration of the racing stage layout based on a single volumetric slice and the integration of checkpoints along the racing track.

Stage

- 2D plane with walls on each side
- Image projected onto the plane

Checkpoints

- Checkpoints define track around the organ border

Methods

In order to encourage users to perform annotations, we explore gamification. In particular, we selected the setup of a racing game to generate an exciting user experience.

The main idea is that the user is driving a race car across a volumetric image slice (**Fig. 1**). In order to create tracks automatically, a simple segmentation method is required. For the first experiments, we chose thresholding to separate fore- and background. Then, we select the largest connected component and perform image processing to automatically extract a closed edge contour. As guidance, checkpoints are spread over the preliminary organ outline to guide the player in equidistant steps along the extracted contour. Based on edge detection [3], a score consisting of accumulated edge pixels is determined automatically as feedback for the player. In order to create a more challenging game experience, additional moving obstacles were added to the course. During driving the player creates a closed contour that is then transmitted from the game client to the server's database.

Results

The game was implemented in Unity3D [4] and released as Android APK Installer (<https://www.medicaldatadonors.org/index.php/scan-racer/>). We chose Google Firebase to store segmentation results on the server (<https://firebase.google.com>). ScanRacer creates a challenging yet rewarding experience for the user. Experienced players are able to create segmentation contours close to the correct segmentation outline. Yet detailed annotations still pose a challenge in this setup which will be addressed by the addition of further game elements. In contrast to many other serious games, the fun component of ScanRacer is very high as reported by test players. A gameplay teaser video (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JNmEGLCyf6w>) demonstrates this in detail.

Conclusion

ScanRacer offers a unique experience for players for volumetric image segmentation. The game was implemented in Unity3D and is available for free download. Sources can be shared at request.

References

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